

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGULUBE****FIRST NAME: MOSES****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2019 on Mac

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Evidence-based academic writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. American versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-31)
4. Compound words (EUCLID 2019, 46)
5. Latin expressions (EUCLID 2019, 51-56)
6. Italics and quotations (EUCLID 2019, 56-61)
7. Chicago bibliography (EUCLID 2019, 53-55)

POLISHING ACADEMIC WRITING SKILLS

1) INTRODUCTION

Learning is indeed a life-long undertaking. I have been struck by how many things I neglected and/or simply glossed over in my professional and academic writing. At the end of an attentive and inquisitive study of the *ACA-401 Coursepack*, I felt justified in my decision to invest in a doctoral study. In the next few pages, I reflect on some of the many things that intrigued me as I interacted with the course material and dug into other complementary published literature.

2) EVIDENCE BASED ACADEMIC WRITING

I have spent over 10 years of my professional life designing, implementing, evaluating and facilitating learning from governance and development programs in different countries. I have equally had the opportunity to participate in several international conferences aimed at unpacking workable pathways to unlocking inclusive and sustainable development. There are many things that continue to captivate my mind each time I dialogue with development practitioners, researchers and donors, among them, is the definition and application of what constitutes evidence of what works (results), proves a

concept and is measurable and appreciated. The definition of evidence and results is contested for several factors “hard evidence, rigorous data, conclusive proof, value for money, evidence-based policy are tantalizing terms promising clarity about what works and what should be funded in international development. Yet behind these terms lie definitional tussles, vested interests and contested worldviews” (Eyben et al. 2015, 2).

The push for methodological rigor and representative evidence in the academic world is equally growing when writing and presenting scholarly publications. A researcher should write an article aimed at persuading his/her readers of an idea or policy option based on evidence (EUCLID 2019, 1). Evidence could be understood here as facts held as truths independent of the researcher’s feelings and beliefs (Turabian 2007, 16). Evidence gathering calls for judicious and diligent research (EUCLID 2019, 2). The foregoing is an invitation to both nascent and established scholars to strive towards intellectual independence and impartiality when analyzing, reporting and presenting research findings. Admittedly, complete intellectual independence and impartiality might not be easily accepted by some schools of thought such as the Kantian one as it postulates that as human beings we interact with and interpret the world around us using *a priori categories* such as quantity, quality and causality (Thomasson 2019). *A priori categories* are ‘intellectual filters’ of reasoning and meaning partly influenced also by the interplay of socialization, education, context and cultural heritage, among other things.

3) PLAGIARISM AND CORRECT REFERENCING

The desire to provide evidence for one’s claims, to prove a point and/or gain some legitimacy, may lead some researchers to involve themselves, knowingly or inadvertently, in committing a serious academic offence by presenting other people’s works as their own (EUCLID 2019, 4). The consequence of plagiarism may be dire depending on where, when and other extenuating factors prevailing at the time the offense is committed and detected. Diligence and high levels of professional ethics are therefore imperative when undertaking academic research to ensure that the intellectual contribution of other thinkers is adequately, timely and appropriately acknowledged. Plagiarism, in all its forms, is therefore wrong and unethical (EUCLID 2019, 5).

When I researched further into different forms of plagiarism, I was enthralled by the categorization of plagiarism by the [University of Oxford](#) (2020) on its students’ website. The University of Oxford has listed eight forms of plagiaristic acts, namely: verbatim, copying and pasting, paraphrasing, collusion, inaccurate citation, failure to acknowledge external assistance, using third parties to write academic assignments and auto-plagiarism. I took some time reflecting on the above list and identified two forms of plagiarism that needed further scrutiny, namely, collusion and failure to acknowledge external assistance. The foregoing two plagiaristic tendencies could be similar in form (involve some sort of collaboration and dialogue) but distinct in substance (carried out by a different cadre of people):

Collusion – consists of illegal forms of student collaboration, non-acknowledgement of help received, be it from fellow students, tutors or other resource persons, in undertaking academic assignments

Failure to acknowledge assistance – is plagiarism because the author deliberately or unintentionally neglects to highlight external support received while working on his or her assignment (University of Oxford 2020).

It could be inferred from the above that collusion as a serious academic offense (EUCLID 2019, 4) is specific to students while failure to acknowledge assistance applies as well to non-student researchers/writers.

I find it astonishing that it is difficult for some intellectuals to acknowledge, where needed, the work of other thinkers considering that there is a lot of guidance regarding how references, bibliographies, footnotes, endnotes and in-text citations could be done. Some of these rules of style include the Chicago Manual of Style, the American Psychological Association (APA) Style and the Harvard Style. Some writers do not recognize the fact that “readers will trust your report only if they trust your evidence and they won’t trust your evidence if they can’t find your source” (Turabian 2007, 35).

4) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

When I read about the nuances that exist between American and British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-32), it made me think about a recent experience I had with two workmates. In February 2019, I was asked by two colleagues John Smith and Adam Shutt (not their real names) to help them prepare for a field visit to one of the project implementation sites in Southern Africa. John is a British national and Adam a US citizen. I had several interesting conversations with these two accomplished gentlemen who sometimes used different words to describe same/similar things. John wanted to know in advance how many *bank holidays* were in February 2019 for the country we wanted to visit as he did not want his trip to coincide with any of them. Adam sent me a separate email asking whether there were any *public holidays* that he could utilize to do some game-viewing and visit a few historical sites.

A day after the above initial exchange, I scheduled a Zoom call where we could discuss some programmatic and logistical aspects of the anticipated field visit. Among other things, John wanted to establish if the price of *petrol per litre* was relatively stable and how much it would cost to visit all sites in a *fortnight*. Before I could respond, I noticed that Adam had raised his hand on Zoom as he wanted to contribute to the discussion. I then invited Adam to share his views. He cleared his throat and said “I have just done a quick search on the internet and realized that the price of *gasoline per gallon* may cost us less than four dollars in many countries in the region so we might just need to budget for less than 3000 dollars for a trip of *two weeks*”.

As we concluded our one-hour Zoom call, the duo wanted to know which of the two forms of English: American or British was more popular. I told them that that was an

interesting question which required an empirical cross-country study. Without avoiding their question and while acknowledging my limited evidence base, I stated that it is common, but not always, to find many people mixing American and British English in one sentence/paragraph even among native speakers of either language deducing from the many exchanges I have had with friends and colleagues from either side of the Atlantic ocean. To illustrate the foregoing, I got an excerpt from a recent conversation with a British colleague who wrote saying “our *organization* has built a state-of-the-art Youth Development *Centre* that will empower a lot of *marginalized* youths with new skills and give them hope for a better tomorrow”. They both laughed and expressed gratitude for a productive discussion.

5) CROSS-CULTURAL ENRICHMENT THROUGH LANGUAGES

Common life is not possible among humans without acceptable ways of communicating concepts, needs, fears, rules and aspirations. Language, in its various forms: sign, verbal and written, is the vehicle through which human beings communicate with one another. As human beings interact with others from different cultural backgrounds and civilizations, they begin to acquire new lifestyles and also develop commensurate categories of communicating their new experiences, thinking and aspirations. Such newly obtained categories of communication may include borrowing and domesticating words from other languages.

a) Latin Expressions in English

I often find it fascinating when I overhear conversations from classmates and workmates arguing about the relevance of knowing a few Latin words considering that it is a dead language. Severally, shortly after such a discussion, I would see some of my colleagues using abbreviations such as etc. (*et cetera*) to denote a continuing list and i.e. (*id est*) to illustrate a point. To avoid confusion, it is recommended that shorter forms of Latin like the two listed above should be avoided in formal and academic writing. Their English equivalents should instead be used such as *and so on* for etc. and *that is* for i.e. (EUCLID 2019, 56).

What some of my above colleagues fail to recognize is that Latin was among the first languages that were used in academic and professional circles for several generations. The foregoing explains why many languages continue to use some Latin words and phrases. Some philosophers, for example, continue to employ a lot of Latin phrases to understand phenomena using *a priori* and *a posteriori* categories of judgement. Similarly, several lawyers proudly make use of *de jure* and *de facto* provisions in defending their clients at risk of being prosecuted. In addition, a botanist in describing a succulent mango fruit, may simply say that the tasty fruit came from a healthy *Mangifera indica* plant.

b) Cross-Fertilization between English and French

Mutual-cultural enrichment has continued to-date as evidenced by the use of foreign words in some languages such as French words in English. A bureaucrat would send a calendar invite to his colleague and send him a follow-up note asking him confirm their *rendezvous* (appointment), sometimes not even realizing that he has just used a word tracing its origin in French. There are indeed several other French words in the English lexicon including *envisage* (from the French verb *envisager*) *souvenir* (from the French noun *souvenir*), *laissez-faire* (a compound noun from two French verbs: *laisser* and *faire*).

French has similarly expanded its lexicon using several English words including: Wi-Fi, internet, cocktail, and so on.

6) CONCLUSION

I have spent the past few days digging into *ACA-401 Coursepack* and other resources I collected to help me sharpen my writing skills both as a doctoral student and as a professional at my workplace where I generate and review a lot of reports for different audiences. As I navigated through the Coursepack, I noticed that it is carefully designed; it builds on what I knew already and progressively drew my attention to other areas that are often neglected in intermediary post-secondary education as I have highlighted in my preceding paragraphs. Furthermore, the response paper has activated and, somewhat, stretched my creative writing skills. Admittedly, I will be consulting these resources regularly as I write and review different publications to ensure appropriate professional and academic rigor.

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